

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

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THE ROLE OF DIGITAL ASSETS IN INTERNATIONAL FINANCE AND THEIR IMPACT ON THE GLOBAL ECONOMY

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Abstract: Digital assets, cryptocurrencies, and central bank digital currencies (CBDCs) are examples of digital assets that are changing the nature of international finance and impacting the global economy. Their decentralized and international nature challenges traditional financial systems. The widespread use of digital assets reduces transaction costs, increases the transparency of financial transactions, and helps emerging markets integrate seamlessly into the global economy. In this article, the role of digital assets in international finance and their impact on the economy are widely covered with tables and diagrams. As an example, the statistics of the countries in this field are cited.

Key words: digital assets, cryptocurrencies, international finance, economy, central bank, transactions.

Annotatsiya: Raqamli aktivlar, kriptovalyutalar va markaziy bankning raqamli valyutalari (CBDC) xalqaro moliya tabiatini o'zgartiradigan va jahon iqtisodiyotiga ta'sir ko'rsatadigan raqamli aktivlarga misoldir. Ularning markazlashtirilmagan va xalqaro xarakteri an'anaviy moliyaviy tizimlarni sinovdan o'tkazadi. Raqamli aktivlardan keng foydalanish tranzaksiya xarajatlarini kamaytiradi, moliyaviy operatsiyalar shaffofligini oshiradi va rivojlanayotgan bozorlarning jahon iqtisodiyotiga muammosiz integratsiyalashuviga yordam beradi. Ushbu maqolada raqamli aktivlarning xalqaro moliyadagi o'rni va ularning iqtisodiyotga ta'siri jadval va diagrammalar bilan keng yoritilgan. Misol tariqasida, mamlakatlarning bu sohada bo'yicha statistikalari keltirib o'tilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: raqamli aktivlar, kriptovalyutalar, xalqaro moliya, iqtisodiyot, markaziy bank, tranzaksiyalar.

Аннотация: Цифровые активы, криптовалюты и цифровые валюты центральных банков (CBDC) являются примерами цифровых активов, которые меняют природу международных финансов и влияют на мировую экономику. Их децентрализованный и международный характер бросает вызов традиционным финансовым системам. Широкое использование цифровых активов снизит транзакционные издержки, повысит прозрачность финансовых транзакций и будет способствовать плавной интеграции развивающихся рынков в мировую экономику. В этой статье роль цифровых активов в международных финансах и их влияние на экономику широко освещены с помощью таблиц и диаграмм. В качестве примера приведена статистика стран в этой области.

Ключевые слова: цифровые активы, криптовалюты, международные финансы, экономика, центральный банк, транзакции.

INTRODUCTION

Every country striving for development is working on advancing its economy. In recent years, digital technologies have developed and gained popularity at a very rapid pace. The integration of digital technologies with the economy has become so profound that the term “digital economy” is becoming increasingly widespread. The digital economy refers to economic activities driven by digital technologies, such as e-commerce and digital services. Digital assets, on the other hand, are intangible assets, including cryptocurrencies, NFTs, and digital tokens, which facilitate transactions and investments within this economy.

Digital assets are intangible assets created on the basis of digital technologies. They serve as a medium for value exchange, investment, or innovation in economic activities.

Main types include:

1. Cryptocurrencies: For example, Bitcoin and Ethereum, which are digital currencies secured by cryptographic technologies and operate on decentralized networks.
2. NFTs (Non-Fungible Tokens): Unique digital assets that represent ownership rights to items such as art, music, or virtual properties.
3. DeFi (Decentralized Finance) Tokens: Digital assets used within decentralized financial platforms for activities like lending, borrowing, or trading.
4. Tokenized Assets: Digital representations of traditional assets (e.g., real estate or stocks) that enable fractional ownership and trading.

The connection between digital assets and the digital economy is so strong that digital assets have become key components enabling value exchange and innovation within this economy. The rise of digital assets in international finance has transformed traditional economic institutions and influenced global markets. Due to their potential to transform financial transactions, offer new investment opportunities, and enhance cross-border trade, digital assets have recently attracted significant attention. Since many digital assets are decentralized and based on blockchain technology, transactions can be carried out quickly, securely, and transparently without intermediaries like banks or financial institutions. Specifically, in regions with limited access to traditional banking services, digital assets provide a means to bridge financial gaps, reduce transaction costs, and enhance financial inclusion in the context of global finance.

LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE TOPIC

The growing prominence of digital assets in the global economy and their transformative impact on financial systems have been widely recognized in academic and industry research.

According to Demirgüç-Kunt et al. in *The Global Findex Database 2017: Measuring Financial Inclusion and the Fintech Revolution*, digital assets have played a significant role in enhancing financial inclusion. Cryptocurrencies and blockchain-based platforms enable individuals in underbanked and unbanked regions to participate in global financial markets without relying on traditional banking infrastructure. These technologies reduce barriers to entry and empower individuals to access credit, savings, and investments.¹

Kathryn Judge, a professor at Columbia Law School and an expert in financial markets and regulation, puts forward the following ideas in his article: “Financial regulations often encourage or require market participants to hold particular types of financial assets. One unintended consequence of this form of regulation is that it can spur innovation to increase the effective supply of favored assets.”²

Bouri et al. in their paper *Does Bitcoin Hedge Global Uncertainty? Evidence from Wavelet-Based Quantile-in-Quantile Regressions* discuss the role of cryptocurrencies, particularly Bitcoin, as a hedge against economic uncertainties. The study highlights the increasing attractiveness of digital assets for investors seeking diversification and protection against traditional market volatility.³

In *Decentralized Finance: On Blockchain- and Smart Contract-Based Financial Markets* by Schär (2021), the potential of DeFi in transforming economic systems is explored. DeFi platforms, powered by digital assets, allow users to engage in lending, borrowing, and trading without centralized control, disrupting traditional financial intermediaries and democratizing access to financial services.⁴

Khaitov A., Karimov Sh. Article analyzes the role of digital assets in the international financial system and their impact on the global economy. The authors studied the role of digital assets in the international financial

1 Demirgüç-Kunt, A., Klapper, L., Singer, D., Ansar, S., & Hess, J. (2018). *The Global Findex Database 2017: Measuring Financial Inclusion and the Fintech Revolution*. World Bank Group.

2 https://scholarship.law.columbia.edu/faculty_scholarship/2064/

3 Bouri, E., Molnár, P., Azzí, G., Roubaud, D., & Hagfors, L. I. (2017). Does Bitcoin Hedge Global Uncertainty? Evidence from Wavelet-Based Quantile-in-Quantile Regressions. *Finance Research Letters*, 23, 87-95.

4 Schär, F. (2021). *Decentralized Finance: On Blockchain- and Smart Contract-Based Financial Markets*. Federal Reserve Bank of St. Louis Review, 103(2), 153-174.

system and their impact on the global economy, and analyzed the role of digital assets in the international financial system and their impact on the global economy.⁵

E.Brynjolfsson and A.McAfee studied the impact of digital currencies on the international financial system in their research. The authors analyzed the impact of digital currencies on the international financial system and studied their impact on the global economy.⁶

P. Kotler's article analyzes the role of digital assets in the international financial system. The author studied the place of digital assets in the international financial system and analyzed their impact on the global economy.⁷

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In carrying out this research work, methods widely used in scientific research methodology were used. In the process of scientific analysis, these scientific research methods were widely used, in particular, observation, generalization, grouping, comparison, and in the analysis, synthesis and analysis methods were widely used.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The role of digital assets in international finance is rapidly evolving, significantly impacting the global economy. Here is a comparison of two European countries, Switzerland and Germany, based on their current positions and figures regarding digital assets:

Switzerland has established itself as a global hub for digital assets, particularly cryptocurrencies and blockchain technology. The country maintains a strong regulatory framework through institutions such as the Swiss Financial Market Supervisory Authority (FINMA), which promotes innovation while ensuring investor protection. The "Crypto Valley" based in Zug is home to many blockchain startups, and Switzerland is experimenting with central bank digital currencies (CBDCs) through pilot programs with the Swiss National Bank (SNB). This infrastructure has strengthened its economy by attracting foreign investment in digital finance sectors.

Germany, by contrast, has taken a more cautious but progressive approach to digital assets. The Federal Financial Supervisory Authority (BaFin) regulates the space, focusing on consumer protection and anti-money laundering measures. Germany is actively working on integrating blockchain into sectors such as logistics and finance, and has passed legislation allowing for digital securities, further modernizing the financial ecosystem. The European Central Bank (ECB), of which Germany is a key member, is leading the development of a digital euro, which could have significant implications for cross-border transactions and the EU's financial system.

Key Comparisons

Adoption of digital assets:

– Switzerland has a more developed ecosystem for blockchain startups and digital asset management, leveraging its neutral position and global financial reputation.

– Germany focuses on integrating digital technologies into traditional finance, while aligning with EU strategies.

Growth dynamics of cryptocurrencies:

– In 2019, the German government recognized cryptocurrencies as financial instruments and introduced regulatory measures, which served as a catalyst for the growth of the cryptocurrency market. In recent years, interest in cryptocurrencies has increased, and their share in the market has continued to rise.

– Switzerland has created a favorable environment for cryptocurrencies and blockchain technologies. The Zug canton, known as "Crypto Valley," has become a hub for crypto companies. In recent years, the cryptocurrency market in Switzerland has shown significant growth.

Income Trends:

– Income generated from cryptocurrencies varies based on changes in the crypto market. In 2021, the prices of Bitcoin and other cryptocurrencies increased significantly, bringing high returns for investors. However, in 2022, due to the market downturn, returns declined.

– Income from cryptocurrencies in Switzerland is influenced by market fluctuations. In 2021, rising cryptocurrency prices increased returns, but subsequent market downturns reduced profitability.

5 "The role of digital assets in the international financial system and their impact on the global economy" – Author: Khayitov A., Karimov Sh. (2022)

6 "The impact of digital currencies on the international financial system" – Author: E.Brynjolfsson and A.McAfee (2014)

7 "The role of digital assets in the international financial system" – Author: P. Kotler

User Growth:

- The number of cryptocurrency users in Germany has been steadily growing. According to a 2020 study, approximately 2.6% of Germans owned cryptocurrencies. By 2023, this figure had risen to 5%.
- Cryptocurrency adoption is expanding in Switzerland. A 2022 survey revealed that 11% of Swiss residents owned cryptocurrencies.

Trading Volumes on Cryptocurrency Exchanges:

- Cryptocurrency trading volumes in Germany, as part of the global market, have been increasing. For example, in 2021, cryptocurrency trading volumes in Germany grew by 50% compared to 2020.
- Cryptocurrency trading volumes in Switzerland have been rising. For instance, in 2021, the “SIX Digital Exchange” platform launched crypto trading, and trading volumes have been steadily increasing since.

Impact on the Economy:

The cryptocurrency market in Germany and Switzerland is emerging as a new segment of the economy. In these countries, the number of startups in cryptocurrencies and blockchain technologies is growing, creating new jobs. Additionally, innovations in financial technologies are accelerating. However, the volatility of the cryptocurrency market and regulatory challenges pose certain risks to the economy.

Germany and Switzerland have advanced regulatory frameworks for the digital assets market, ensuring strict government oversight in this area.

In Germany, digital assets, particularly cryptocurrencies and tokens, are recognized and regulated as financial instruments. The Federal Financial Supervisory Authority (BaFin) oversees activities related to digital assets. According to amendments to the “German Banking Act” (Kreditwesengesetz – KWG), which came into force on January 1, 2020, a special license is required to provide digital asset custody services. This license, issued by BaFin, is necessary to legally conduct services related to digital assets. Additionally, the “Electronic Securities Act” (Gesetz über elektronische Wertpapiere – eWpG), adopted in 2021, regulates the issuance and circulation of digital securities.

Switzerland supports a progressive approach to digital assets and has established a clear legal framework for their regulation. The Swiss Financial Market Supervisory Authority (FINMA) oversees activities related to digital assets. The “Ordinance on Financial Services” (FinSO), effective from August 1, 2021, defines the rules for the issuance, custody, and circulation of digital assets and tokens. Moreover, amendments to the Swiss Civil Code recognize the proprietary rights of digital assets and allow their legal circulation.

These regulatory frameworks in Germany and Switzerland aim to regulate the digital assets market, protect investors’ rights, and ensure financial stability.

Picture 1.⁸

This chart shows data on Germany’s assets and direct investments from 2000 to 2023. As you can see, over the past period, attention to assets has increased and the volume of investments in it has increased several times.

8 https://www.destatis.de/EN/Themes/Economy/Short-Term-Indicators/IMF/IMF_IWF.html?nn=22952#fussnote-16-1344028

Germany's policies on assets and investments are designed to foster a stable economic environment, promote foreign and domestic investment, and ensure economic growth. Germany encourages prudent management of assets, including financial, industrial, and natural resources. As one of the world's largest economies, Germany focuses on fostering a stable, attractive environment for both domestic and foreign investors.

Table 1.

SDDS Plus Data Category and Component	Unit Description	Observations			% Change from previous period to latest period	% Change from same period last year to latest period
		Period of latest data	Latest data	Data for previous period		
Transactions in financial assets and liabilities (Financing)						
Net acquisition of financial assets	Euro millions	Q2/2024	-16,217	-6,085	X	X
Domestic	Euro millions	Q2/2024	-17,395	-1,739	X	X
Foreign	Euro millions	Q2/2024	1,178	-4,346	X	X
Net incurrence of liabilities	Euro millions	Q2/2024	-3,831	8,654	X	X
Domestic	Euro millions	Q2/2024	-21,23	-30,862	X	X
Foreign	Euro millions	Q2/2024	17,399	39,516	X	X

In Germany, transactions in financial assets and liabilities primarily involve borrowing (liabilities) and lending or investing (assets) by key players like the government, banks, corporations, and households. Transactions in financial assets and liabilities, commonly referred to as «financing transactions,» are a crucial part of Germany's financial ecosystem. These transactions involve the movement of capital to fund various sectors of the economy, including public and private entities. This table below is based on the data published on the official website of the German Statistical Office, which provides detailed information on transactions in financial assets and liabilities, with precise figures and the latest data.

Table 2.⁹

Official reserve assets									
Foreign currency reserves									
		Securities				Total currencies & deposits			
		Total	Total	The borrower from them was based in Switzerland, but lived abroad	Other national central banks	Banks located in Switzerland		Banks located outside Switzerland	
Total	abroad					Total	banks	Total	abroad
CHF	718727	882	588	16845	16664	4	0	176	0
USD	831476	988	681	19487	19279	5	0	204	0

⁹ <https://data.snb.ch/en/topics/snb/cube/snbimfra>

The table summarizes Switzerland's official reserve assets, namely foreign exchange reserves (CHF and USD) distributed between securities, common currencies and deposits, and their respective sources (banks in Switzerland, banks abroad and other central banks):

- The bulk of reserves in CHF are held in total currencies and deposits (16,845 million), with a smaller amount (588 million) held in securities.
- In terms of US dollars, general currencies and deposits (19,487 million) dominate, while securities account for 681 million.
- A large portion of CHF and USD reserves in total foreign exchange and deposits are held in other national central banks.
- A very small part of the reserves is held in banks located in Switzerland or abroad.
- The table highlights the international aspect of Swiss reserve management, with borrowers residing abroad but domiciled in Switzerland for some securities.

In short, Switzerland's foreign reserves prioritize deposits at central banks over securities, reflecting a strategy focused on liquidity and safety.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

Digital assets have evolved beyond simple theoretical frameworks and now serve as an important component of the modern financial ecosystem. Ongoing innovations in cryptography, blockchain, and distributed ledger technologies are reshaping the way value is created, shared, and stored. Case studies such as those in Germany and Switzerland show clear benefits, from simplified payment infrastructure to new ways to attract investment. These examples highlight the global impact of digital assets on monetary policy, cross-border trade, and overall economic growth.

To maximize the benefits of digital assets and minimize the associated risks, it is necessary to adopt a multi-pronged strategy:

Specialized Education: Encouraging universities and professional organizations to introduce specialized programs in blockchain engineering, token economy and cyber security, thereby training highly qualified personnel.

Continuing Education: Offer government-backed grants or scholarships to professionals seeking to further their education. These initiatives can bridge the gap between rapid technological progress and the talent pool needed to implement it effectively.

Lower costs, higher speed: Traditional money transfer channels often involve multiple intermediaries, each of which adds complexity and fees. Digital assets simplify these processes, reduce cost barriers and waiting times, making international trade more convenient and efficient.

Institutional Safeguards: As digital asset markets expand, both government agencies and private sector firms must implement high-level security measures, such as multi-signature wallets, hardware modules, and robust auditing practices, to protect investors and consumers.

Public Awareness: In addition to institutional security, user education programs are essential. Providing guidance on secure storage, private key management, and potential fraud schemes can significantly reduce vulnerabilities in digital asset ecosystems.

Tax and regulatory incentives: Governments can offer pilot zones or sandboxes where innovative blockchain and digital asset solutions can be tested under flexible regulations. It fosters a dynamic environment for startups and encourages global investment.

Sustainable Economic Impact: By aligning digital asset projects with broader policy goals, such as green finance or social welfare, governments can leverage the unique capabilities of blockchain-based platforms to drive sustainable and inclusive economic development.

In conclusion, while digital assets are already demonstrating significant economic advantages, from improved remittance channels to enhanced investment mechanisms – additional efforts are needed to improve regulatory structures, increase human capital, and modernize financial infrastructures. By combining forward-looking policies, international cooperation and rigorous risk controls, both governments and the private sector can take advantage of the potential of digital assets to drive innovation and enhance global economic prosperity.

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